

Effect of Moisture Absorption on the Expansion Coefficient α

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ABSTRACT

It is known that composites with epoxy and other matrices, when exposed to humidity, readily absorb moisture from the atmosphere by a diffusion-controlled process. In this study the moisture absorption behaviour of a model resin and carbon fibre reinforced composite has been evaluated. The effect of moisture in the form of the temperature dependence of the coefficient of thermal expansion ($\alpha_m(T)/T$, $\alpha_t(T)/T$) and the thermal strains in $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminates has been studied. Comparison between experimental and predicted values is discussed.

KEYWORDS

Water-absorption; thermal expansion coefficients; thermal strains; epoxy resins; carbon fibre composites

INTRODUCTION

Polymer-matrix fibre reinforced composites have a tendency to absorb moisture, particularly in hot/wet environments. The absorbed water in composite materials is known to have significant effects on the physical and chemical properties of matrix as well as on the long term performance of composite structures.

Adamson postulated [1, 2] that the transport of moisture into a glassy thermosetting resin below T_g is a three-stage process in which the absorbed moisture first occupies the free volume present in the form of voids. In the second stage, water becomes bound to network sites causing swelling. Finally, in the third stage, water enters the densely crosslinked regions. This causes the T_g to be reduced. However, with the water located in different regions of the resin, there is a strong probability that the transition will occur over a larger temperature range. In service this will occur slowly because of the rate of diffusion of water into the structure will be governed approximately by Fickian kinetics.

Most applications of CFRP require laminates that have plies with the fibres oriented in more than one direction and use resins that cure at high temperatures. As a result of cooling from these cure temperatures, residual strains develop within a laminate. For unidirectional laminate they are present at the micromechanical level because of a mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre and matrix. For angle-ply laminates, they result from the mismatch in properties of the plies of differing orientation [3].

It has been shown [4] that on cooling from a temperature T_1 to a lower temperature T_2 the thermal strain which develops in the longitudinal direction of the transverse ply of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composite, ε_{il}^{th} , is given by:

$$\varepsilon_{il}^{th} = \frac{E_l b (\alpha_t - \alpha_l)(T_1 - T_2)}{(E_l b + E_t d)} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where E_l and E_t are the Young's modulus of the unidirectional plies parallel to the fibres (the longitudinal or 0° , l) and perpendicular to the fibres (the transverse or 90° direction, t) respectively. α_l and α_t are the linear expansion coefficients of the 0° and 90° plies. b and $2d$ are 0° and 90° ply thicknesses respectively. T_1 is the temperature at which strain is first built into the laminate, and is

dependent upon the viscoelastic nature of the matrix resin. T_2 is the temperature at which ε_{it}^{th} is measured.

The use of 0°/90° composite laminates to determine residual strain is well established [5, 6]. The thermal expansion mismatch between the two plies results in a thin beam becoming curved, in the way of a bimetallic strip. By measuring the radius of curvature of the beam (ρ), $(\alpha_t - \alpha_l)(T_1 - T_2)$ [7] can be calculated.

It is necessary for predictive purposes to build up a data base on the effect of moisture on $\alpha_m(T)$, $\alpha_t(T)$ and T_l . Commercial epoxy resins are mostly based on blends of tetraglycidyl 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane epoxy (MY721) with other epoxies of different functionality and cured with 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (DDS). Therefore, in this study we have concentrated on a model system which will form the basis for understanding more complex blends.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy resin is a tetrafunctional epoxy monomer (Ciba Geigy MY721) crosslinked with an aromatic amine, 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (DDS). These components were commercial products, and were used as received without purification. The matrix was prepared by mixing the components in an oven at 80 °C and stirring continuously until a homogeneous mixture was achieved. The composition of the mixture was 76 wt% of MY721 and 26 wt% of DDS, yielding an amine/epoxide ratio of 0.62.

The mixture was degassed for 2 hr at 80°C, then was poured into a mould, cured at 130°C for 1h, heating 3°C every 5 minutes up to 160°C and up to 180°C at a heating rate 1°C/min, finally cured for 2h. The specimens were polished to a thickness of 2.5 mm and cut into samples of 8 x 60 mm².

The Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) (Du Pont Instruments) was used to assess the degree of cure of the matrices. The heating rate in all the cases was 10 °C/min for both cured and uncured samples. The degree of cure was calculated from the difference between the enthalpy of cured and uncured samples.

Composite materials were prepared from Tenax HTA 5131 carbon fibres, which we wound onto a frame and impregnated with the resin/hardener blend. Subsequently laminates of 0°/90°₂ and 0°₄ were prepared in a pressclave. The beams, which were cut to the dimension of 100 x 200 mm², were found to have a fibre volume fraction, V_f , of 0.5 ± 0.01 .

The stress free temperature T_l , was determined by raising the temperature of an unbalanced beam at a heating rate of 5°C/min with a 5 min dwell at each temperature, until it became perfectly flat.

The samples were dried in vacuum oven at 50°C under full vacuum until a constant weight was attained. Drying for two or three weeks under these conditions was considered sufficient for the samples. They were conditioned at 100%RH, 96% RH and 75% RH at 50°C. The relative humidity levels were established in glass chambers containing saturated salt solutions of K₂SO₄ (96% RH) and NaCl (75% RH) and for the 100% RH the samples were immersed in distilled water. The moisture content, M_t , was monitored using an electrobalance accurate to 10⁻⁵ g.

The temperature dependence of coefficient of thermal expansion ($\alpha_m(T)/T$, $\alpha_t(T)/T$) between -50 and 300°C was determined using TMA. Thermal expansion data were expressed as polynomials and differentiated to obtain dependence of α_m and α_t .

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analyser (DMTA) was used to measure T_g, over the range from 50 to 320°C temperature, in the dry and conditioned samples; the heating rate of 5°C/min, and a frequency of 1 Hz.

RESULTS

1. Resin Matrix Properties

The degree of cure was estimated from the residual exotherm to be 85.3%

The sorption and desorption curves for the MY721/DDS at 50 °C in different relative humidities are given in Figures 1a and 1b respectively. These curves show Fickian-type diffusion in the first stage of the process, continue to absorb water in the long term. The desorption curve, however, behaved in a Fickian manner but all of the weight gain could not be recovered. As shown in Table 1 the residual concentration after desorption in vacuum, 3500 hr at 50°C and 350 hr at 140°C, is significant.

Fig 1. Moisture absorption isotherm and desorption isotherm for matrix MY721/DDS exposed to different relative humidities at 50°C

RH	Residual water, %	
	@110°C	@ 140°
Immersed	0.825	0.789
96%	0.798	0.764
75%	0.403	0.367

Table 1. Residual concentration of water in matrix MY721/DDS after desorption in values at 50°C and further heating in vacuo at 140°C

Figures 2a to 2d show the temperature dependence of the resin expansion coefficient at different moisture contents and different environmental conditions. According to Ogata [8] the interstitial and hole free volumes change with the degree of crosslinking and these volumes determine drops in α in the rubbery region.

Above a certain threshold of moisture content ($\approx 3.5\%$ in this case) no further changes in α_t are observed. The coefficient of thermal expansion is not constant below T_g .

Fig 2. Temperature dependence of the coefficient of thermal expansion at different moisture contents in MY721 DDS resin. (a) and (b) Immersed in distilled water at 50°C; (c) and (d)Suspended above a saturated solution of 75% RH and 50°C

Typical dynamic mechanical spectra are given in Fig 3a and 3b, for a dry sample and when at the maximum water concentration. From these plots, two main transitions were observed for this dry resin. The transition centered at about 220°C has been identified as the “ ω ” transition [9] and can be attributed to unreacted molecular segments and/or inhomogeneities in the material arising from regions of dissimilar crosslinking densities. Finally, the higher temperature transition centered approximately at 280°C has been identified as the “ α ” transition and can be attribute to the glass transition. It is readily seen that the peaks broaden upon absorption of water.

Fig 3. Tan δ versus temperature for MY721/DDS. (a) When the sample is dry and after 5000 hr at 50°C and 75% RH; (b) The sample is dry and after 5000 hr at 50°C and 96% RH

2. Composite Properties

A plot of the moisture absorption curve for the MY721-HTA5131 based composites immersed in distilled water and 50°C is shown in Fig. 4. This figure also shows the comparative results for the resin and for a predicted value of the composite. These results were calculated using the rule of mixtures, with V_f equal to 50%.

Fig 4. Moisture absorption isotherm for MY721-HTA5131 based carbon fibre composite, MY721 and predicted value for the composite immersed in distilled water at 50°C

The expansion coefficients of resin sample and the composite in the transversal direction are shown in Fig. 5a, the coefficient of thermal expansion for the unidirectional composite in the longitudinal direction can be ignored, because of its small and negative value. From this plot we can observe that α_t is approximately 50% lower than α_m , which corresponds to the volume fraction of the matrix in the composite. In Fig. 5b is possible to observe the change in the expansion coefficient for the composite in the transverse direction when the samples have been immersed in distilled water and exposed to 50°C.

Fig 5. Expansion coefficients. (a) Comparison of linear expansion coefficients for resin matrix and transverse expansion coefficient; (b) Changes in the transverse expansion coefficient for the composite

The temperature dependence of the radius of curvature of a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ asymmetric beam can be monitored by recording its displacement from flat. Figure 6 shows a typical plot of the displacement, δ , against temperature as unbalanced beam was heated or cooled in an oven.

Fig 6. Temperature dependence of the displacement, δ , of a freely bending $0^\circ/90^\circ$ MY721-HTA5131 beam. Dry sample

The change in beam displacement with moisture content (M_t), for $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams, was investigated and from this data the residual thermal strain at each moisture content was calculated using equation 1, (Table 2). The values for b and d were 0.9 and 1.1 mm respectively.

Sample	δ mm	ρ Mm	E_l GPa	E_t GPa	T_1 C	ϵ_{ii}^{th} %
0.000	6.0	833.33	237.5	6.9	190	0.37
1.376	5.0	1000.00	214.8	6.4	110	0.29
1.504	3.3	1515.15	203.4	6.2	80	0.19

Table 2. Residual strain in $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ data for MY721-HTA5131 based carbon fibre composite, at different M_t

A plot of the thermal strains against temperature was constructed from the deflection length and temperature, when the sample was dry and when it had absorbed some water from the environment.

From the coefficient of thermal expansion at different temperatures and equation 1 the predicted thermal strains were determined, we can observe the results of this prediction in Fig. 7 a

Fig 7. Temperature dependence of the residual thermal strains. (a) From bending beam and the predicted result with α , predicted 1 with $\alpha(T)/T$ and predicted 2 with α constant; (b) Change in the thermal strain with the moisture absorbed

DISCUSSION

1. Moisture Absorption and desorption

Figure 1a shows experimental results for water uptake of MY721-DDS after immersion or conditioned at 50 °C and different relative humidities. From this curve, we can observe, firstly, that the absorption curve can be treated as linear with the square root of time from the beginning to almost three per cent weight gain or higher. This linearity suggests that absorption is predominantly diffusion controlled in this region. Secondly, the final water uptake proceeds very slowly and after few percentage the graphs have a nonlinearity. This nonlinearity of the absorption process is indicative of non-Fickian diffusion. As the RH increases the concentration of absorbed water increases too.

Figure 1b is a typical desorption curve. The residual weight of a sample which had been immersed in water at 50°C, after desorption at 50°C in vacuum was 0.83% when the sample was immersed in distilled water, after increasing the desorption temperature at 140°C, in vacuum, this was reduced by 5% to 0.79%. Assuming that the residual weight is made up from hydrogen-bonded water and that which is chemically reacted, we consider that the majority of the residual ‘water’ is probably associated with the latter.

2. α , T_g and Thermal Strains

Previous studies on this model resin [10] have reported that the T_g is reduced by sorbed moisture. Similarly, the “ α ” transition exhibited a dependence on moisture. As can be seen, increasing moisture content not only results in a shift of the “ α ” transition to lower temperatures, but also a noticeable broadening.

The absorption of water also increases the expansion coefficient of the matrix resins (especially at elevated temperatures) (Fig. 2). The coefficient of thermal expansion is increased significantly up to 3% of moisture where it remains approximately constant. A moisture content of 2.5% can be defined as the threshold for absorption into highly crosslinked regions with swelling. Recently Karad et al observed a similar threshold value for the rate of swelling to become equal to the rate of absorption [11].

For the laminate, the transversal coefficient of thermal expansion increases with increasing moisture content in a manner consistent with the resin behaviour.

Attempts to predict the thermal strain in a 0°/90°/0° from a complete description of the expansion coefficient temperature dependence were unsuccessful. Since T_1 was observed to have the same value, we conclude that the matrix within the composite may not have the same identical thermal mechanical properties. Further study required to confirm that this is the case. Sized fibres have been used for composite fabrication. Sizing resins can lead to a reduction in T_g of an interphase region. This is a possible explanation of this effect.

The 'effective' T_g is defined as the temperature at which the 0°/90° beam ceases to be flat and corresponds to the temperature at which strain is first built into the laminate. The values of T_1 obtained from these experiments are showed in Table 2. As the moisture content in the composite increases the displacement of the beam, δ , decreases. We can observe from this table, that when the moisture content in the sample rises T_1 decreases, but these values of "effective" T_g are not the same as values of the T_g obtained from DMTA, but for the prediction of the thermal strains the T_g considered was the "effective" value. From Fig 7 b we can observed that the thermal strains decrease when the sample has absorbed some water and there is certain linearity in this decrease.

CONCLUSION

Moisture absorption by a model epoxy resin matrix has been studied in detail. The moisture diffusion occurs in a Fickian manner until the concentration exceeds 2.5/3% when swelling effects became important. This was also observed in the data for the thermal expansion coefficient (α_m). The thermal strain in model laminates is reduced by moisture absorption. Attempts at prediction need refinement since the appropriate values of T_1 and $\alpha_m(T)$ in the composite do not appear to be same as those of the resin.

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